

Selection of bioclimatic parameters

A common practice when using MaxEnt is to take measures to reduce collinearity between predictors (Elith et al. 2010b). There are different approaches to achieve this goal (Dormann et al. 2012). In our work, the selection of original predictors was carried to minimize the linear correlation within the set of selected predictors. At the first stage of selection, correlation groups of bioclimatic predictors were identified (i.e., groups of parameters, the correlation within which is higher than the correlation between parameters from different groups). Then, one parameter was selected from each correlation group that demonstrated the greatest importance for constructing a distribution model of the studied species. Among the selected predictors, additive selection was carried out at the stage of selecting modeling parameters, along with determining other parameters to achieve the best quality of the model.

Fig. 1. Heat map of the correlation matrix (Pearson linear correlation coefficient) of all 19 bioclimatic parameters

Fig. 1 shows a heat map of the correlation matrix of 19 bioclimatic parameters in the spatial region of background point generation: from 30° to 60° N and from 30° to 179° E. As can be seen in this diagram, temperature and humidity parameters are clearly distinguished. Within these groups, individual subgroups can also be distinguished.

More precise identification of correlation groups was performed using cluster analysis (Hennig et al. 2015; Wierzchoń and Kłopotek 2018). In this work, we used the HDBSCAN (Hierarchical Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise) clustering algorithm, a modern, highly efficient method that allows identifying clusters even in complex data (Campello et al. 2013; McInnes and Healy 2017). A special feature of this algorithm is its ability to independently identify the number of clusters, as well as noise points – samples that cannot be assigned to any cluster. Noise points can be interpreted as clusters of a unit size. Nineteen bioclimatic parameters were used as samples, and the statistic $d = 1 - r$ was used as a measure of distance between them, where r is the value of the Pearson linear correlation coefficient calculated for the series of bioclimatic parameter values at the grid nodes within the region of background point generation. The implementation of the HDBSCAN algorithm in the hdbscan package for Python was used.

The quality of clustering was determined using the average value of the silhouette coefficients (Rousseeuw 1987). Its values were determined for all values of the hyperparameter ϵ of the HDBSCAN algorithm in the range from 0 to 10 with a step of 0.1. In all cases, the average value of the silhouette coefficients was 0.513 and the clustering results were identical.

Two clusters were identified: cluster 1 (BIO1-3, BIO5, BIO6, BIO9-11) and cluster 2 (BIO12-14, BIO16-19). Four noise points were also identified: BIO4, BIO7, BIO8, BIO15. It can be seen that clustering clearly separates temperature and humidity parameters.

As can be seen in Fig. 1, the noise points BIO4 (temperature seasonality, standard deviation $\times 100$) and BIO7 (temperature annual range BIO5-BIO6) can be combined into one group, since the correlation coefficient between them is 0.96, which is quite explainable by their similar nature. Also, although the clustering algorithm assigned BIO2 to cluster 1, its weak correlation with other members of this cluster, except for BIO3, allows us to allocate it to a separate group.

Thus, we identified the following correlation groups:

1. BIO 1, BIO 3, BIO 5, BIO 6, BIO 9-11
2. BIO12-14, BIO16-19

3. BIO2
4. BIO4, BIO7
5. BIO8
6. BIO15

To select one parameter from these groups (except for groups 3, 5 and 6), a modeling of the territory of possible distribution was carried out using all 19 parameters. MaxEnt software version 3.4.1 was used. 20 models were created for 20 previously created sets of background points. When running the algorithm, the option to evaluate the importance of predictors using the jackknife test was set. The remaining modeling parameters had default values. The selection was based on 4 tests: gain contribution, permutation test and two jackknife tests (training gains with and without variable). The obtained data are presented in Table 1. Based on the majority principle, the following parameters were selected and used in further modeling and calibration of the model: BIO1, BIO2, BIO4, BIO8, BIO12, BIO15. It is worth noting that BIO8 showed very low importance in all tests.

Table 1. The importance of 19 bioclimatic parameters for modeling the range of *Ixodes pavlovskyi*, according to the results of four tests

Variable	Gain contribution	Permutation importance	Training gain with only variable	Training gain without variable (the least is best)	Number of tests in which variable has the best result in its group
BIO1	3.6556	12.9499	0.6822	1.9689	2
BIO3	5.2211	9.4559	0.3098	1.9474	1
BIO5	1.7891	1.6565	0.4558	1.9963	0
BIO6	11.7937	0.3959	0.5805	1.9985	1
BIO9	0.2133	0.621	0.5711	1.9855	0
BIO10	2.2254	1.4462	0.4661	1.9943	0
BIO11	10.7979	5.5634	0.5872	1.9755	0
BIO12	7.9662	23.8569	0.447	1.9238	2

BIO13	3.0302	1.5154	0.2563	1.9916	0
BIO14	24.8759	0.2502	0.6212	1.9957	1
BIO16	0.7978	4.6111	0.2609	1.9798	0
BIO17	4.1245	0.5461	0.6871	1.9929	1
BIO18	5.8278	0.0053	0.3414	1.9971	0
BIO19	0.7501	1.4927	0.516	1.9935	0
BIO4	5.0644	19.3478	0.4497	1.9558	4
BIO7	0.0782	0.0423	0.3408	1.9953	0
BIO2	2.528	1.9654	0.291	1.9764	
BIO8	0.2333	0.4347	0.2611	1.9873	
BIO15	9.0277	13.8433	0.4916	1.8954	

Color designations

Correlation group 1
Correlation group 2
Correlation group 3
Single-element correlation groups

Fig. 2. Pairwise scatter plots of six selected bioclimatic parameters and values of their linear correlation coefficients r

Fig. 2 shows the pairwise scatter plots and the values of the linear correlation coefficients for the six selected parameters. As can be seen, the correlation between them is quite low, except for the pair BIO2-BIO15, but in this case the value of the correlation coefficient (0.67) is acceptable. However, this circumstance and the fact that BIO2 was isolated from cluster 1 “manually” despite the results of cluster analysis require additional verification of the necessity of this parameter’s participation in modeling, as well as the parameter BIO8.

Selection of modeling parameters

To obtain an effective model of species distribution, it is necessary to select model parameters using modeling quality metrics (Warren and Seifert 2011). In this work, two MaxEnt parameters were selected: a set of climate variables and their transformation functions.

It is known that MaxEnt uses not only raw untransformed variables but also their transformations using different functions: quadratic, product, hinge and threshold (the latter was not used in this work). The results of these transformations are usually called features. To reduce the complexity of the model and avoid overfitting, it is recommended to choose only those types of transformations that result in the most effective model.

In this paper, untransformed and quadratic features were used in all test variants. The selection was performed from four options: 1) with both product and hinged features, 2) only with product features, 3) only with hinged features and 4) without both product and hinged features.

As stated earlier, further study is required to determine the possibility of using bioclimatic parameters BIO2 and BIO8 in constructing the *I. pavlovskyi* distribution model. For this purpose, modeling was performed on four sets of bioclimatic parameters: all six, without BIO2, without BIO8, and without both.

All other MaxEnt parameters had default values. In particular, the regularization parameter beta had a value of 1 and prevalence was equal to 0.5.

Thus, the selection was made from 16 sets of modeling parameters. On each of them, the modeling of potential ranges of *I. pavlovskyi* was carried out for all three study periods using 20 sets of background points. The quality of the obtained models was assessed using three indices: Akaike Information Criterion corrected (AICc), Boyce Index (BI) and Area Under Curve (AUC).

Akaike Information Criterion corrected (AICc). This index determines the balance between the accuracy of the model, calculated as the likelihood function of raw predictions on samples, and its complexity expressed through the number of features of the model (Akaike 1992). In this study, we used the corrected Akaike Information Criterion (AICc), which is recommended for small sample sizes and includes an appropriate correction (Burnham and Anderson 2002; Johnson and Omland 2004). AICc was calculated using the formula:

$$AICc = 2K - 2\sum(\log p) + 2K(K+1)/(n-K-1),$$

where K is the number of features with non-zero coefficient λ (the contribution coefficient of a feature to the final model of the distribution function of habitat suitability; due to the application of L1 regularization, a certain number of these coefficients turn to zero), n is the number of detection points, p is the raw prediction values for the detection points.

AICc was calculated for the results of each MaxEnt run on one of the 20 background point sets. The obtained AICc values were averaged. The model with the lowest average AICc value was considered the best. To identify the reliability of the difference between AICc for different model variants, the Student's t-test for pairwise dependent samples was used, since the same 20 background point sets were used in all variants (Boslaugh 2013). It was conducted as follows. For each possible pair of model variants, the difference between the AICc values for the same background point set was calculated. The resulting sample of 20 values was tested using the t-test for the difference between its average value and 0. In the overwhelming majority of cases, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test showed that the hypothesis of a normal distribution of these samples is acceptable. A similar assessment was also applied to the other two used model quality indices.

Boyce Index (BI). This index was specially developed to assess the quality of presence-only species distribution models. It was first proposed in the work (Boyce et al. 2002). The original version of calculating this index consists of dividing the range of the target model value of species suitability (in the case of MaxEnt – cloglog prediction) into several non-overlapping intervals and calculating for each interval i the value

$$F_i = (n_i/N)/(a_i/A),$$

where n_i is the number of samples with predicted suitability within interval i , N is the total number of samples, a_i is the number of raster points of the studied spatial region with predicted suitability within interval i , A is the total number of raster points of the studied spatial region.

Next, the smoothness of the curve of the dependence of the values of F_i on i is estimated. For these purposes, the Spearman nonlinear correlation coefficient is usually used. The Boyce Index value is a value of the correlation coefficient used. The greater is the value of BI, the better the model.

In paper (Hirzel et al. 2006) a more advanced version of calculating Boyce Index was proposed, in which the suitability range is not divided into non-overlapping segments, but a moving

window is used. This allows one to obtain a smoother curve even on a not very large number of samples.

In our study, this variant of calculating the Boyce Index was applied using the `ecospat.boyce` function from the `ecospat` package for the R data analysis environment. The default values of the calculation parameters were used: the window width was 0.1, the number of window steps was 100. The Spearman coefficient was used as the correlation coefficient.

Since the prediction of the distribution area was made for three periods, BI was calculated based on fragments of the corresponding rasters of the predicted suitability values corresponding to the region of background point generation for the three studied periods for each set of background points. The detection points with the dates of finds corresponding to the prediction period served as samples. Thus, 60 BI values were calculated for each variant of the model parameters. For the final selection of the model, averaging was performed both within the periods and for all 60 values. Statistical assessment of the reliability of differences between the model variants was performed according to the technique described earlier for AICc with the feature that pairwise assessments were performed within individual periods; no assessments were made between BI sets for different periods.

Area Under the Curve of Receiver Operating Characteristic (AUC ROC or simply AUC). This index is widely used in assessing the quality of continuous classification, when assessing, for example, the probability of belonging to a class (Hastie et al. 2016). The ROC curve is constructed based on the confusion matrix containing the number of true positive (TP), true negative (TN), false positive (FP) and false negative (FN) samples. This is a plot of the true positive rate $TPR=TP/(TP+FN)$ against the false positive rate $FPR=FP/(FP+TN)$ at each threshold setting. AUC is the area under this curve and displays the number of correctly classified samples for all threshold values.

In the literature, there are many examples of criticism of the use of AUC to assess the quality of SDM (Peterson et al. 2008; Moreno-Amat et al. 2015). AUC requires samples of both positive and negative classes. MaxEnt estimates AUC by treating background points as negative samples. We used AUC as a complement to the two previous indices, which were the main ones in model selection.

The training AUC values calculated by MaxEnt itself were analyzed. The average values obtained for each set of background points were estimated. The reliability of the difference between different pairs of models was estimated using the previously described statistical procedure.

Table 2. Quality indices of *I. pavlovskyi* distribution models with different sets of bioclimatic parameters and features. The best values for each index are shown in bold underlined font. The selected combination of model parameters is shown in gray background.

Set of bioclimatic parameters	Features		AICc	Boyce Index					AUC
	product	hinge		1961-1980	1981-2000	2001-2020	mean	std	
BIO1, BIO4, BIO12, BIO15	+	+	1301.6	0.8647	0.8268	0.9332	0.8749	0.0539	0.9327
	+	-	1262.8	0.7704	0.8663	0.9511	0.8626	0.0904	0.9232
	-	+	1309.1	0.8571	0.8303	0.9076	0.865	0.0393	0.929
	-	-	1254.9	0.7657	0.8288	0.9662	0.8536	0.1025	0.9232
BIO1, BIO2, BIO4, BIO12, BIO15	+	+	1418.4	0.8594	0.8345	0.9262	0.8734	0.0474	0.951
	+	-	<u>1222.4</u>	0.8902	<u>0.9076</u>	0.9314	<u>0.9098</u>	<u>0.0207</u>	0.95
	-	+	1419.9	0.8349	0.8149	0.9384	0.8628	0.0663	0.9472
	-	-	1234.6	0.8814	0.7628	0.7744	0.8062	0.0654	0.9368
BIO1, BIO4, BIO8, BIO12, BIO15	+	+	1406.5	<u>0.9302</u>	0.7936	0.8898	0.8712	0.0702	0.939
	+	-	1260.1	0.8556	0.8387	0.9515	0.882	0.0608	0.9273
	-	+	1706.1	0.9134	0.8168	0.9038	0.878	0.0532	0.9357
	-	-	1256.2	0.7665	0.8264	<u>0.9666</u>	0.8532	0.1027	0.9232
BIO1, BIO2, BIO4, BIO8, BIO12, BIO15	+	+	2082.1	0.8058	0.8435	0.9272	0.8588	0.0621	<u>0.9531</u>
	+	-	1227.9	0.8126	0.8605	0.6973	0.7901	0.0839	0.9517
	-	+	1756.8	0.879	0.8118	0.924	0.8716	0.0565	0.949
	-	-	1236.4	0.8408	0.7303	0.821	0.7973	0.0589	0.9355

Table 2 shows the results of assessing the quality of modeling the distribution of *I. pavlovskyi* tick for 16 sets of model parameters. A model with the following combination of parameters was selected as the most effective: a set of five bioclimatic parameters (BIO1, BIO2, BIO4, BIO12, BIO15) and a set of feature with product and without hinge. The AICc value for this combination of parameters was the lowest. The BI value was the highest for the period 1981-2000, the third for the period 1961-1980 and the seventh for the period 2002-2021. However, the average BI value was highest with the smallest standard deviation of values across periods. The AUC value was the fourth. But this index, as mentioned earlier, is not indicative in SDM. In addition, the difference in AUC for this combination of parameters from higher values was small, although statistically significant. The other two indices for this set of parameters also had a statistically significant difference from the values for other options.

The results of modeling the *I. pavlovskyi* distribution calculated with this selected set of parameters for the 20 sets of background points were averaged, mapped and used in further analysis. Also, for all three study periods, standard deviations (std) of habitat suitability were calculated and mapped as a measure of model uncertainty. As well, mean values of MESS (Multivariate Environmental Similarity Surfaces; Elith et al. 2010a) were calculated and mapped as a measure of the correctness of modeling the species distribution outside the actual distribution region.

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